

**Parenting Skills as Correlates of Mental Wellbeing of School-Aged Children in Owerri
Educational Municipal, Imo State Nigeria**

Ibeabuchi, Glory Ifeyinwa (Ph.D)

Department of Special Needs Education
Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education
Owerri, Nigeria
ibeabuchiglory@yahoo.com

and

Ugwumba, Eucharia Ukamaka (Ph.D)

Department of Educational Foundations and Management
Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education Owerri, Nigeria
eucharia.ugwumba@yahoo.com

Abstract

This study aimed to investigate whether parenting skills influence the mental well-being of children in the Imo State, Owerri Educational Municipal area. Three main questions and hypotheses were used to direct this study. The study used descriptive surveys of the correlational style. The area examined was the Owerri Municipal Council, which functions as the capital of Imo State in Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the primary three pupils in the government-owned primary school in Owerri Municipal Council. There are 1242 children in the 24 government-owned primary schools in Owerri Municipal Council. Using a random selection technique, a sample of 242 students, representing 10% of the entire population, was chosen for this investigation. The Parental Skills Questionnaire (PSQ) and the Warwick Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale (WEMWBS) were the two tools used to gather data for this study. Internal consistency reliability indices of 0.74 and 0.81 were obtained by testing the reliability coefficient using the Cronbach Alpha formula. Two hundred and forty-two (242) copies were distributed in total. To address the research objectives and test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance, Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation was used to evaluate the data. The result revealed that a strong positive and significant relationship exists between parental responsiveness, a moderate positive relationship between parental demandingness, as well as a weak positive relationship between permissive parenting and mental wellbeing of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal. In light of the study's findings, parents were advised to foster an emotionally healthy atmosphere in the house, which can help kids feel supported, loved, and appreciated. This can improve kids' mental health and overall wellness.

Keywords: Parenting Skills; Parental Responsiveness; Parental Demandingness; Permissive Parenting; Mental Wellbeing

Introduction

In today's environment, the mental well-being of children has become an area of increasing concern for parents, educators, and policy makers alike, while offering a wealth of educational and rehabilitation opportunities, also presents unique challenges, such as overcoming academic pressure. Social competition, exposure to digital media, and reduced family interaction time. These factors can significantly impact the psychological health of school-aged children, making parenting more critical than ever. Parenting skills, including emotional support, effective communication, discipline, supervision and consistency, serve as a foundation for a child's mental and emotional development.

As for a child, they begin reporting feeling mentally healthy if they can cope with issues when they arise and successfully acquire social skills associated with problem-coping strategies. Research states that mentally healthy children are capable of coping with day-to-day tasks at school and home, thereby contributing positively towards the quality of life and health. With the appropriate support, children tend to develop highly and positively with successful life outcomes by leading an independent life. The parent, or caregiver in the role of a parent, is one of the most integral social circles of the child, who greatly influences the child's development towards independence and a healthy, successful life achievement. Without proper support, parents will have poor parenting skills, which will tell on their children, alongside fostering harmful relationships, inclusive of violence, discrimination or deprivation (Berzonsky, 2016).

Literature Review

Who is a Child?

A child is an individual who has not reached adulthood. A child is a human who is younger than the age of 18 according to "The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of a Child" (2013). In this regard, a child is someone who is between the ages of 0-8 and is receiving full emotional and physical attention from his or her parents. So it suggests that the child's upbringing and child rearing starts at the age of zero and extends up to eight years. In common terms, child rearing refers to up bringing a human being from infancy through childhood and adolescence to adulthood and educating the child in societal morals and values (Berk, 2020). It entails helping the child grow up to be a contributing member of both the family and society. It involves taking care of a child in his formative years. According to Douglas (2002), a child's development is influenced by his surroundings and the type of instruction he receives from his parents. The act of raising a minor is known as child rearing. In addition to meeting the child's fundamental requirements, it actively shapes the child's character, personality, abilities, and physical and mental health. In other words, a child's destiny is greatly influenced by the type of upbringing they received from their parents.

Parenting Skills

A child's parents, who are the child's biological mother and father, are responsible for meeting the child's emotional and physical needs in society. Parents raise or bring up children and are their primary source of information. Children are kept alive not just by the provision of necessities like food, clothes, and shelter, but also by the active development of their personalities, character traits, and emotional and physical health. The nature vs nurture controversy is a popular topic of discussion when discussing what makes an individual who they are (Douglas, 2002).

The reality of the situation is that the child is much of what he is and that he/ she has been shaped by his/her parents and child rearing, and the variables that come into play there are crucial. Parents are their children's friends and advisors. They serve as "reflectors, supporters, active communicators, and sources of assistance, feelings, opinions, and ideas for the children." Ononuju (2014) asserts that parents are objects of affection. Ononuju goes on to say that parents provide their children with stability, support, and physical and emotional care throughout their early and later years. Well-behaved parents are child trainers because parents set an example for their kids, and the house is a teaching laboratory. It is the responsibility of parents to instil in their children the morals, values, taboos, culture, norms, and traditions of the community. To put it another way, parenting "involves caring for and meeting the child's needs."

Parenting involves raising and bringing up children from infancy through adulthood. Additionally, Kendiora and Leary (1993) characterise parenting as duties a parent does or refuses to do that could potentially impact the child, and these include attending to physical needs, play, discipline, education, and creating a positive emotional climate. It takes on the daily care for children until they can be responsible for themselves. Lamborn (2002) discusses that parenting has less to do with the "attempts of parents to control or direct the behaviour of children". Thus, parenting is a complicated and straneous activity comprised of many distinct behaviours that sequentially and interactively affect development in offspring. More specifically, it refers to the rearing, educating, morally teaching, and instilling values in a child from infancy to adulthood (Berk, 2020). It means, also, taking that child and shepherding him through life to become a valued member of society. Parenting refers to care given to children or, specifically, a child during their early life. For this paper, parenting is defined as the process of caring for children and assisting them in growing and learning the use various parenting skills.

The expression of parental skills provides "care and nurture" to the child, which promotes their optimal development. According to Hall and Elliman (2003), a child's growth and development can be determined by the appropriate use and understanding of parenting techniques. When properly implemented, the youngster develops into a well-adjusted person who will be welcomed by society. Every parent in society must be concerned and prioritise their provisions for their child's needs because the ultimate objective of parenting is making sure an individual is responsible, decent and

productive, and would in turn be a blessing to his or her parents. It is in providing affection, moral and emotional support, inspiration, physical care, and direction. This should all be given to allow each child to reach his or her full potential. Unground parenting has always, and will always, create uncertainty in any child's development. This is also why the struggle to attempt to become a successful parent is so critical and will be the most important work one will ever do in their lifetime (William, 2014).

Parenting Responsiveness

Parenting Responsiveness, which is one specific component of parenting skills according to Maccoby and Martin (2013), is defined as "the degree to which parents encourage individuality, self-regulation, and self-assertion by their attentiveness, sensitivity, and willingness to tolerate the needs of their children" (Baumrind, 2021). The way parents recognise and address their children's needs is the main emphasis of this type of responsiveness. Specifically, sensitivity, acceptance, approbation, affection, comfort, and engagement are all components of parental responsiveness (Bogenschneider and Pallock, 2018; Campbell et al., 2017). Numerous studies show that creativity and parental response are positively correlated. For instance, Lim and Smith (2018) stated that parenting skills that had a higher acceptance level were associated with great levels of mental and psychological well-being. Conversely, highly responsive parenting styles, such as permissive and authoritative, were positively associated with mental well-being, while low responsiveness parenting styles, such as authoritarian parenting style, were negatively correlated with mental well-being (Miller et al., 2012; Fearon et al., 2013). Moreover, findings imply that one aspect of parenting skills is a predictor of mental well-being among school-aged children. In addition, support of parents' involvement, which was considered an important element of parental responsiveness, was associated with a positive mental well-being among school-aged children (Liang et al., 2021), as well as parental warmth (Guo et al., 2021). In this sense, based on these results, parental responsiveness could arguably provide a more democratic atmosphere that promotes in children the ability to be self-sufficient and autonomous when discovering novelties and new situations that might be represented by a conducive context to enhance mental wellbeing.

Parental Demandingness

Parental demandingness is viewed with a high level of authoritarianism but a low level of responsiveness. Parental demandingness teaches blind obedience and respect for authority. Expectations set for children tend to be rigid, and when not met, a child's behaviour will be reprimanded and not often corrected. Parents who use this method tend to have discontented, detached, and distrustful children (Baumrind, 2021). These children tend not to develop good emotional regulation in later years. Children are not permitted to negotiate or defend their behaviours, and they are limited in their autonomy and decision-making, while the primary goal of the parent is to instil obedience and the recognition of their power and authority. This parenting style is described as comprising enforced rules and edicts at the discretion of the parent as well as strong control over the child's autonomy (Baumrind, 2016). Such parenting strives to regulate children's behaviour to a specific and usually non-relative norm of behaviour, often an absolute one (Baumrind, 2021). These

parents also frequently utilised demands as a form of discipline and minimally permitted their children to exercise autonomy. They also display little child-parental affection and warmth (Thompson, Hollis & Dagger, 2003). Children of this kind of parents are expected to have a negative correlation with children's mental wellbeing; that is, children's self-esteem and mental contentment and security as well as negative attitudes about the world are likely to be low, while factors related to adherence to standards are likely to be high (Loeber et al., 2020).

Permissive Parenting

Permissive parenting, in contrast, has minimal demands and heightened responsiveness. It is loving and caring but not overbearing, domineering, or disciplinary (Pettit et al., 1997). Permissive parents try to respond to their children's wishes and acts with indulgence and are inclined to give their children as much control over their activities as possible (Baumrind, 2021). Permissive parenting is defined as when parents do not impose limits and do not require children to exhibit developmentally appropriate behaviour. As a result, it is anticipated that this parenting style would have a detrimental impact on kids' psychological health, and kids of permissive parents exhibit characteristics like narcissism, social irresponsibility, and self-centred drive (Berzonsky, 2016; Ramsey, Watson Biderman & Reeves, 2014). So, permissive parenting can ultimately be detrimental to children's psychological welfare. In addition, this parental skill has been consistently associated with a range of adverse developmental outcomes over the years, such as future behavioural problems (Vanderfaellie et al., 2013).

Concept of Mental Wellbeing

"Mental wellbeing" and "mental health" are key concepts with no easy definition. The World Health Organisation (2014) defines mental health as a condition of well-being in which a person recognises their potential, can manage everyday stressors, works effectively and efficiently, and gives back to their community. Other phrases that are used in the literature include psychological, mental, or subjective well-being, good mental condition, and mental capacity and well-being (de Cates, Stranges, Blake, & Weich, 2015). Mental health is defined within the context of a larger constellation of behaviours that produce a healthy, happy, meaningful life (World Health Organisation, 2014). In conjunction with physical health, "health" also includes mental health. Yet, factors determining general health and those determining mental health are distinct. In particular, being physically healthy usually means being free from diseases or disorders (Fusar-Poli et al., 2020). According to the World Health Organisation (2014), "mental health is more than the absence of mental illnesses or mental diseases". For instance, the absence of abscesses or tumours in an MRI scan does not necessarily correlate with a person's mental well-being. Mental wellbeing and mental illness are, in this sense, distinct from each other and "not inversely correlated" (de Cates et al., 2015). It suggests that patients may experience mental illness while also exhibiting high levels of mental well-being.

Mental health was, at one point, conceived as a constellation of symptoms of positive affect and positive functioning (Keyes, 2013). In this sense, Keyes (2013) has proposed that mental health can be

assessed using a continuum, with mental disorders at one end and mental well-being at the opposite. However, more recent work has come to view mental wellbeing as distinct from mental illness and mental distress (de Cates et al., 2015). For instance, mental distress among patients may occur due to stressful events. But this distress could be seen as a normative response and a positive coping mechanism. One example of this may be a grieving patient. Grief and even depression are common reactions to loss. Additional definitions of mental well-being focus on different behaviours and activities. More specifically, Ryff (2013) defines mental wellbeing as the presence of six sub-domains, including a sense that life is meaningful, personal growth and positive development, quality social relationships, perception of mastery over life challenges, positive self-image and purpose in life.

To be mentally healthy, one must be able to handle stress in any situation, play at their house and in the community, and attend school without feeling upset, nervous, or depressed (Mental Health Foundation, n.d.). Achieving one's full potential and a child's development are also dependent on good mental health. Significant life changes for the child that might result in a mental health problem are starting school or moving house. Puberty is a developmental stage during which an enormous amount of emotional and physical upheaval can occur for the child, placing him or her at a particular risk for psychological difficulties. Experiences may include a parent's divorce, the death of a significant individual, natural disasters, violence, and war. The exposure to violence, in that sense, represents one of the main factors that contribute to children developing mental health issues. On a global scale, children are increasingly subjected to violence with an acutely detrimental effect on their psychological health and well-being (Flannery, 2018). These experiences could be directly linked, exposed to community, home, or schoolphysical, sexual, or emotional violence or indirectly through exposure to violence, events on social media, television or radio.

Statement of the Problem

Child rearing and care are very important for optimal child development. This is made possible through the appropriate use of parenting skills in society. The knowledge of such skills will help parents in ensuring proper child upbringing and training. The fact that childhood is the root cause of many mental health issues is becoming more and more obvious. Family characteristics, such as the level of care parents give their kids, can have a significant impact on how they develop in their early years, either positively or negatively. Identifying the most effective ways to support parents through intervention is a major challenge. High standards must be met when providing early interventions to provide kids with the best start in life. Thus, this paper sought to determine the relationship between parental skills and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal, Imo State.

Objectives of the Study

Generally, the purpose of this study was to investigate parental skills as correlates of mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal, Imo State. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Determine the extent to which parental responsiveness relates to the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal.
- ii. Ascertain the extent to which parental demandingness relates to the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal.
- iii. determine the extent to which permissive parenting relates to the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal.

Research Questions

- i. The study answered the following questions: What is the relationship between parenting responsiveness and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal?
- ii. What is the relationship between parenting demandingness and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal?
- iii. What is the relationship between permissive parenting and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal?

Methodology

The study utilised a descriptive survey design of the correlational type. This design is thought to be appropriate for the study since it looks at the strength of correlation and direction of correlation (positive or negative) of the relationship between multiple independent variables and a dependent variable. The study's focus was the "Owerri Municipal Council, the capital of Imo State". Situated in the southeast region of Nigeria, Imo State has 27 local government areas, including the one being examined.

The study's population consisted of all three primary school students at the Owerri Municipal Council's government-owned primary school. There are 1242 pupils in the 24 government-owned primary schools in Owerri Municipal Council. Using a simple random sampling procedure, a sample of 242 students, representing 10% of the entire population, was chosen for this investigation. Two instruments were used for data collection in this study, namely the questionnaire titled "Parental Skills Questionnaire PSQ). And the WEMWBS scale. (The instrument consisted of 4 parts. Part A sought to gather the demographic information of the respondents while part B elicited information on parenting skills with 15 items structured on four (4) point likert type scales of "Strongly Agree (SA) Agree (A) Disagree (D) Strongly Disagree (SD)" with assigned weights of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively for positive questions and the reverse (1, 2, 3 and 4) for negative questions." Part C elicited information on Mental well-being using the "Warwick Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale" (WEMWBS) with 14 items. The reliability coefficient was tested using the Cronbach Alpha formula, and internal consistency reliability indices of 0.74 and 0.81 were obtained. Following this, 242 copies were distributed. To prevent loss

during transit and to guarantee that the chosen respondents were accountable for the data, the researcher immediately collected the completed questionnaires from the respondents. To test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance and to answer the research objectives, the Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation was used to analyse the data.

Decision Rule for Correlation Tests

Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)	Strength	Direction
+0 – +0.34	weak	Positive Relationship
-0 – -0.34	weak	Negative Relationship
+0.35 – +0.59	Moderate	Positive Relationship
-0.35 – -0.59	Moderate	Negative Relationship
+0.60 – +0.99	Strong	Positive Relationship

If the calculated value is greater than the table value ($\alpha = 0.05$). Decision: Reject the null hypothesis.

Results

Research Questions 1

What is the relationship between parental responsiveness and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal?

Table 1: “Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between parental responsiveness and mental wellbeing of school-aged children”

	Model	N	r-cal.	Decision
Parental Responsiveness	1	242	0.768	Strong relationship
Mental Wellbeing				

Data in Table 1 shows the “Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation Analysis” demonstrating the relationship between parental responsiveness and mental well-being of school-aged children. The result shows r-cal. Of 0.768, which indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between parental responsiveness and mental wellbeing of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal.

Research Questions 2

What is the relationship between parental demandingness and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal?

Table 2: “Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between teachers’ use of instructional materials and pupils’ performance in Mathematics”

	Model	N	r-cal.	Decision
Parental Demandingness	1	242	0.530	Moderate relationship

Mental Wellbeing

Data in Table 2 shows the Pearson’s “Product Moment Correlation Analysis” of the relationship between parental demandingness and mental wellbeing of school-aged children. The result shows r-cal. Of 0.530, which indicates that there is a moderate positive relationship between parental demandingness and mental wellbeing of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal.

Research Questions 3

What is the relationship between permissive parenting and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal?

Table 4.3: “Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between permissive parenting and mental wellbeing of school-aged children “

	Model	N	r-cal.	Decision
Permissive Parenting	1	380	0.334	Weak relationship
Mental Wellbeing				

Data in Table 3 shows the “Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation Analysis” of the relationship between permissive parenting and mental well-being of school-aged children. The result shows r-cal. of 0.334, which indicates that there is a weak positive relationship between permissive parenting and mental wellbeing of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between parental responsiveness and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal.

Table 4: “Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation Analysis of the Significant Relationship between parental responsiveness and mental well-being of school-aged children”

	Model	N	r-cal.	R-crit.	Df	p-value	Decision
Parental Responsiveness	1	242	0.768	0.0875	240	0.000	Reject H0 ₁
Mental Wellbeing							

Table 4 indicates that the p-value (0.000) is below the 0.05 benchmark. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that the mental health of school-age children in Owerri Educational Municipality is significantly correlated with parental responsiveness.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between parental demandingness and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal.

Table 4.7: “Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the Significant Relationship between parental demandingness and mental wellbeing of school-aged children”

	Model	N	r-cal.	R-crit.	Df	p-value	Decision
Parental Demandingness	1	242	0.530	0.0875	240	0.000	Reject H ₀ ₂
Mental Wellbeing							

Source: Field Data, 2023.

Table 5 above indicates that the p value (0.000) is less than 0.05; p value < 0.05 level. As a result of this, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between parental demandingness and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant relationship between permissive parenting and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal.

“Table 4.8: Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation Analysis of the Significant Relationship between permissive parenting and mental wellbeing of school-aged children”

	Model	N	r-cal.	r-crit.	Df	p-value	Decision
Permissive Parenting	1	242	0.334	0.0875	240	0.000	Reject H ₀ ₃
Mental Wellbeing							

Source: Field Data, 2023.

The result presented in Table 6 revealed that the p value (0.000) is less than 0.05; p value < 0.05 level. As a result of this, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between permissive parenting and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal.

Discussion of Findings

According to the data analysis summary for research question 1, there was a significant positive correlation. Parents' attention to and response to their children's needs make this feasible. Additionally, hypothesis 1 showed a strong correlation between school-age children's mental health and parental responsiveness in Owerri Educational Municipality. This finding is in tandem with the initial findings of Bogenschneider and Pallock (2018 and Campbell *et al.* (2017), who noted that parental responsiveness includes behaviours such as “*sensitivity, acceptance, approval, affection, comfort, and involvement*”. The results corroborate those of Lim and Smith (2018), who discovered a correlation between high levels of mental well-being and parenting abilities marked by greater

acceptance. Miller *et al.* (2012) and Mehrinejad *et al.* (2015) findings also indicated that parenting skills with high responsiveness were positively correlated with mental well-being. According to the findings, responsive parents may create a democratic atmosphere that fosters children's independence and autonomy in experimenting with novel concepts and circumstances, which may serve as a foundational setting for enhancing mental health.

Hypothesis 2 further revealed that there was a significant relationship between parental demandingness and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal. This conclusion is made possible by the fact that these parents typically give their kids very little autonomy and discipline them with demands. Additionally, they are cold and uncaring in their interactions with children. This finding is consistent with that of Loeber *et al.* (2020), who discovered that this style of parenting has a negative correlation with children's mental health; that is, children of demanding parents are more likely to have a low opinion of themselves, be less comfortable and content, and have negative attitudes towards the world; on the other hand, they are more likely to perform well when it comes to standard-following. This implies that these children tend not to develop good emotional regulation in later years. Children are not permitted to negotiate or defend their behaviours, and they are limited in their autonomy and decision-making, while the primary goal of the parent is to instil obedience and the recognition of their power and authority.

In testing hypothesis three, the result revealed that there was a significant relationship between permissive parenting and the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal. This was made possible by permissive parents, who make an effort to respond in a way that is both nonpunitive and supportive of their kids' goals and behaviours while also letting them manage their activities to the greatest extent feasible. This result is consistent with previous research by Ramsey, Watson, Biderman, and Reeves (2014) and Berzonsky (2016), who discovered that children of permissive parents display traits like self-focused motivation, a tendency towards narcissism, and social carelessness, and that this parenting style is negatively linked to children's mental health. This finding also lends support to Vanderfaillie *et al.* (2013), who found that permissive parenting is potentially harmful for children's mental well-being. Furthermore, several detrimental developmental consequences, including long-term behavioural issues, have been consistently associated with such parental skills.

Summary and Conclusions

Based on the results, the study concludes that parenting skills such as parental responsiveness, demandingness, as well as permissive parenting significantly relate to the mental well-being of school-aged children in Owerri Educational Municipal.

Recommendations

- i. The following suggestions were offered in light of the study's findings and conclusions:

- ii. Children's mental health and general well-being can be improved when parents foster a loving, supportive, and respected emotional environment in the home.
- iii. Schools and policymakers should encourage greater parental involvement in children's academics.
- iv. The Government should introduce and promote parenting works that focus on effective communication, discipline and strategies and academic support at home.

References

- African Charter on the rights and welfare of the child. OAU Doc CAB/LEG/24.9/49/ (1990) @ 2013 African Commission on human and Peoples' Rights.
- Baumrind, D. (2021). Current patterns of parental authority. *Dev. Psychol*, 4:1 103.
- Baumrind, D. (2021). The influence of parenting style on adolescent competence and substance use. *J. Early Adolesc.* 11 56–95
- Baumrind, D. (2016). Parenting: The discipline controversy revisited. *Fam. Relat.*;45:405–414.
- Berk, L. (2020). *Development throughout the lifespan (3rd Ed.)*. U.S.A. Allyn and Bacon.
- Berzonsky, M. D. (2014). Identity style, parental authority, and identity commitment. *J. Youth Adolesc.*;33:213 220.
- Bogensneider, K., Pallock, L. (2018). Responsiveness in parent-adolescent relationships: Are influences conditional? Does the reporter matter? *J. Marriage Fam.* 70 1015–1029
- Campbell, K., Thoburn, J. W., Leonard, H. D. (2017). The mediating effects of stress on the relationship between mindfulness and parental responsiveness. *Couple Family Psychol.* 6 48–59.
- de Cates, A., Stranges, S., Blake, A., & Weich, S. (2015). Mental well-being: An important outcome for mental health services? *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 207(3), 195–197
- Douglas, R. (2022). Helping children learn to use the toilet. In Todd, C. M. (Ed.). *Family day care connection: Urbana-campaign*. University of Illinois Press. Co-operative Extension Services
- Fearon, D. D., Copeland, D., & Saxon, T. F. (2013). The relationship between parenting styles and creativity in a sample of Jamaican children. *Creat. Res. J.* 25 119–128.
- Flannery, D. J. (2018). Here's how witnessing violence harms children's mental health.
- Fusar-Poli, P., de Pablo, G. S., De Micheli, A., Nieman, D. H., Correll, C. U., Kessing, L. V., & van Amelsvoort, T. (2020). What is good mental health? A scoping review. *European Neuropsychopharmacology*, 31, 33–46.
- Guo, J. J., Zhang, J., & Pang, W. G. (2021). Parental warmth, rejection, and creativity: the mediating roles of openness and dark personality traits. *Personal. Individ. Differ.* 168:110369.
- Hall, D. & Elliman, D. (2013) 4th (Ed.). *Health for all children*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Kendiora, N. and Leary, J. (1993). *Parenting and Discipline Life Matters*. Retrieved April 2006 from <http://lifematters.com/parenting-and-discipline.asp>
- Keyes, C. L. M. (2013). Promoting and protecting positive mental health: Early and often throughout the lifespan. In C. L. M. (Ed.), *Mental well-being: International contributions to the study of positive mental health* (pp. 3–28). Springer Science + Business Media.

- Lamborn, I.S. (2015). *Contraceptive patterns and adolescent sexual behaviour*. Family Planning Perspectives.
- Liang, Q. L., Niu, W. H., Cheng, L., & Qin, K. X. (2021). Creativity outside school: The influence of family background, perceived parenting, and after-school activity on creativity. *J. Creat. Behav.* 205 56–60
- Lim, S. & Smith, J. S. (2018). The structural relationships of parenting style, creative personality, and loneliness. *Creat Res. J.* 20 412–421.
- Loeber, R., Green, S. M., Lahey, B. B., Frick, P., J. & McBurnett, K. (2020). Findings on disruptive behaviour disorders from the first decade of the developmental trends study. *Clin. Child Fam. Psychol. Rev.*, 3:37 60.
- Maccoby, E. E., Martin, J. A. (2013). Socialisation in the context of the family: Parent-child interaction. *In Handbook of Child Psychology*, eds Mussen P. H., Hetherington E. M. (New York, NY: Wiley), 1–101.
- Mehrinejad S. A., Rajabimoghadam S., Tarsafi M. (2015). The Relationship between Parenting Styles and Creativity and the Predictability of Creativity by Parenting Styles. *Proc. Soc. Behav. Sci. U.S.A.* 205 56–60.
- Mental Health Foundation. (n.d.). *Children and young people*. Retrieved August 2018, from <https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/a-to-z/c/children-and-young-people>
- Miller A. L., Lambert A. D., Neumeister K. L. S. (2012). Parenting Style, Perfectionism, and Creativity in High-Ability and High-Achieving Young Adults. *J. Educat. Gifted* 35 344–365.
- National Population Commission (NPC) (2011). Federal republic of Nigeria and ICF international *Nigeria Demographic and Health survey*.
- Ononuju, J.N. (2014). *The family and parenting in Nigeria's social development*, Imo Polly Amadi, Publication Nigeria.
- Pettit G.S., Bates J.E., Dodge K.A. (2017). Supportive parenting, ecological context, and children's adjustment: A seven-year longitudinal study. *Child Dev.*, 68:908–923
- Ramsey, A., Watson, P.J., Biderman, M. D., Reeves, A. L. (2016). Self-reported narcissism and perceived parental permissiveness and authoritarianism. *J. Genet. Psychol.*, 157:227 238.
- Thompson, A., Hollis, C., & Dagger, D. R. (2013). Authoritarian parenting attitudes as a risk for conduct problems: Results from a British national cohort study. *Eur. Child Adolesc. Psychiatry*, 12:84 91.
- Vanderfaellie, J., Van Holen, F., Vanschoonlandt, F., Robberechts, M., & Stroobants, T. (2013). Children placed in long-term family foster care: A longitudinal study into the development of problem behaviour and associated factors. *Child Youth Serv. Rev.* 35:587 593.
- Winsler, A., Madigan, A. L., & Aquilino, S. A. (2015). Correspondence between maternal and paternal parenting styles in early childhood. *Early Child Res. Q.*, 20:1 12.
- World Health Organisation. (2014). *Promoting mental health: Concepts, emerging evidence, practice: Summary report*. Retrieved January 2, 2024, from https://www.who.int/mental_health/evidence/en/promoting_mhh.pdf